

REPORT ON SCIENTIFIC PAPERS

[Deliverable 8.2]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the scientific publications produced during the life of the ER4STEM project. Scientific publications are one of the evaluation criteria of the success of ER4STEM project “*Number of peer reviewed articles related to the project published in scientific magazines or at scientific conferences*” (DoW pp 7). Thus the role and main objective of this deliverable is to show how ER4STEM orchestrated the scientific dissemination of the project outputs so that a) we ensured wide coverage in terms of targeted audiences, topics and venues b) we highlighted all the different facets and aspects that constitute the ER4STEM approach and c) we identified venues for publications that were relevant to our work but they could also broaden our horizons and help us enrich, refine and evolve our ideas.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

The scientific publications reported in this deliverable draw from all the work done in the project. Specifically, most publications report on the learning process documented and analysed in of **WP6** (Evaluation), in the context of educational activities designed in **WP4** (Pedagogical design and innovation for Educational Robotics) and in workshops – competitions organized and implemented in the context of **WP2** and **WP3**. There are also publications reported and planned focusing on the pedagogical design of Educational Robotics activities (WP4), on the technologies implemented in the project (SLurtles and Hedgehog – WP5), and on the creation of a curriculum for educational robotics (WP2). This deliverable and specifically aspects related to access to the publications and the respective empirical data, relates to D.8.1 Data management plan.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document is structured in four sections. Section 2 aims at showing how ER4STEM scientific publications aimed at covering all the facets of ER4STEM approach by offering an overview of the publication venues and their focus and by organizing thematically the publications providing their abstract and keywords. In section 3, we present a list of all publications. Finally in section 4 we discuss how the project handled access to the scientific publications according to the consortium agreement and the data management plan (D.8.1)

2 SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

In this section we describe and discuss the strategy for the scientific dissemination of the project. First we refer to the Venues (i.e conferences, workshops symposia) ER4STEM was represented. The description of Venues aims at showing how we worked towards reaching the most relevant but also wide audience for your work. The second section presents shows the focus of the project's publications organized in themes which map to the key-ideas and outputs of the project.

2.1 VENUES

Conferences reach very quickly a wide audience, allow for networking on the spot and offer a ground for reflection, enrichment and consolidation of ideas. This is the reason why ER4STEM focused primarily on conferences. The aim was to raise awareness and interest to the ER4STEM approach for robotics and STE(A)M, developing our approach through interaction with other experts in the field and establishing connections so that there is an audience which could follow up our work that will be published in journals and book chapters.

Since 2016, project partners attended 17 different conferences. With respect to the outreach of these conferences 14 were international events, two were regional events -the Hellenic Conference on Innovating STEM Education (HiSTEM) (Greek) and the Sixth Austrian Robotics Workshop (ARW 2018) (Austrian)- and one regional conference with international participation: "11th International Conference "ICT in Education", 19-21 October 2018, Thessaloniki, Greece".

The conferences in which ER4STEM partners participated are related to a number of different outputs of the project, aiming at a wide outreach at the scientific community. Specifically, the focus of the conferences involve: Robotics in Education, Robotics and maker movement, STEM; Mathematics-Engineering, Design, Teacher professional Development, Research approaches, ICT in Education. Our selection strategy of these conferences, developed around two main criteria:

- **Target communities:** As shown in the table and the graph below (see table 1, and graph 1) , the conferences we attended address two types of audiences: a) the robotics community and b) scientific communities which show an interest in robots because of their impact in teaching and learning (e.g. STEM Education, ICT in Education etc). This combination allows scientific dissemination and discussion of ER4STEM ideas in depth (robotics community) and in breadth (relationship to other domains of application of robotics) allowing dissemination of our work to other domains of applications of robotics (e.g. STEM, Interaction Design; Teacher professional development etc)
- **Key ideas and outputs of ER4STEM:** This criterion was applied to identify conferences with a focus on different facets of innovative work done in the project: i.e. mixed research methodology to explore the role of robotics in learning STE(A)M concepts, instructional design tools for educational robotics activities, teaching and learning with robotics, design of educational material and resources, design of robots, engagement with robots as making activity etc.

A list of the conferences and their focus is provided in the table below:

Table 1 ER4STEM presence in conferences and conference focus

ID	Name of the Conference	Focus
1	Inclusive Robotics for a better Society Conference (INBOTS) http://inbots.eu/inbots-conference-2018-2/	Robotics
2	International Conference on Robotics and Education RiE 2016, 2017 http://rie2016.info/ http://rie2017.info/	Educational Robotics
3	EduRobotics 2016 Educational Robotics in the Makers Era http://edurobotics2016.edumotiva.eu/	Educational Robotics and making
4	Sixth Austrian Robotics Workshop (ARW 2018) http://www.roboticsworkshop.at/	Robotics
5	26th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN). http://www.ro-man2017.org/site/node/3.html	Robotics – Human Robot Interaction
6	International Conference on Engineering Education (ICEED) 2016 http://enter.uitm.edu.my/iceed2017/	STEM (Engineering Education)
7	10th Congress of European Research in Mathematics Education: CERME10 http://cerme10.org/	STEM (Mathematics)
8	II IEEE World Engineering Education Conference (EDUNINE2018) http://edunine.eu/edunine2018/eng/	STEM (Engineering Education)
9	IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (IEEE EDUCON 2018) http://educon-conference.org/educon2018/	STEM (Engineering Education)
10	Hellenic Conference on Innovating STEM Education (HiSTEM) 2016 http://stemeducation.upatras.gr/histem2016/	STEM Education
11	International Workshop on Computational Thinking and Coding skills https://lnu.se/en/meet-linnaeus-university/current/events/2017/international-workshop-on-computational-thinking-and-coding-skills-in-schools/	STEM
12	ESERA 2017. Educational Science Education Research Association Conference 2017 http://www.esera2017.org/	Educational Science – Educational Research
13	European Conference on Educational Research (ECER) 2017, 2016 https://eera-ecer.de/ecer-2017-copenhagen/ https://eera-ecer.de/ecer-2016-dublin/	Educational Research
14	Constructionism 2018 http://www.constructionism2018.fsf.vu.lt/	Making – STEM, Digital Learning
15	11th International Conference “ICT in Education”, 19-21 October 2018, Thessaloniki, Greece	ICT in Education

	http://hcicte2018.csd.auth.gr/en/index.html	
16	Interaction Design and Children (IDC) 2016, 2017 http://www.idc2016.org/ http://idc2017.stanford.edu/	Design
17	Re(s)ources 2018 http://international.ens-lyon.fr/re-s-sources-2018-conference-359038.kjsp	Teacher professional development – use of resources

Graph 1. Paper type and conference focus

In the graph above we offer an overview of the papers we submitted in the 17 conferences, organizing papers according to their type and conferences according to their focus.

2.2 THEMES

In this section we attempt to organize thematically the conference papers (only) identifying 6 main categories around which the scientific publications evolved and these include a) the ER4STEM approach b) Supporting the teaching practice c) Student Engagement with Robotics and STEM d) ER4STEM technologies e) Storytelling and f) STEM learning.

ER4STEM approach

The papers included in this section provide the conceptual approach to **Educational Robotics** (Lammer et al 2016) and an **initial analysis of the framework** (Angel-Fernandez and Vincze 2018; Angel-Fernandez et al 2018) which -according to the DoW- was meant to underline, the development of activity plans (WP4), the evaluation of the learning process (WP6) and the implementation of workshops (WP2). A journal publication for the ER4STEM framework is planned to be submitted within 2018.

ER4STEM Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics: 2016

Lara Lammer, Wilfried Lepuschitz, Chronis Kynigos, Angele Giuliano and Carina Girvan

International Conference on Robotics and Education RiE 2016

Keywords: Educational robotics; framework; teachers; repository

"Robotics is a popular vehicle to introduce young people to science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) with various approaches worldwide that use robotics to teach or entertain or both, accompanied by various tools and repositories. However, the stakeholders involved have different goals and methods, thus difficulties in finding common ground; e.g. the focus in most cases is on increasing interest in STEM, but research methods are unspecified or vague; or despite the vastness of offerings, teachers are reluctant to incorporate activities in the classroom. In this paper, we introduce the Educational Robotics for STEM (ER4STEM) project that will realise a creative and critical use of educational robotics to maintain children's curiosity in the world: an open and conceptual framework will bring three main stakeholders of educational robotics – teachers, educational researchers and organizations offering educational robotics – together in a user- and activity centered repository."

Towards a Formal Definition of Educational Robotics: 2018

Julian M. Angel-Fernandez and Markus Vincze (TuWien)

Sixth Austrian Robotics Workshop (ARW 2018)

There is an increasing number of articles, web pages, robotic kits and other materials that are using the term Educational Robotics (ER) to refer to the use of robots in education, however the current definition of ER is still vague and open to misinterpretation. Therefore, anyone can claim that their work falls in the category of ER just because robots are involved. Despite all benefits of robotics, its incorrect use may be counterproductive. Therefore, the incremental use of the term ER is meaningless if it is not used correctly. Consequently, a concrete and precise definition of ER is required to support the development of it. This paper presents a first attempt to develop a concrete definition of ER, which describes all fields of study that constitutes it and how they are related between them. The definition is the result of the experience acquire during the participation of the European project Educational Robotics for STEM (ER4STEM).

Towards a Framework for Educational Robotics: 2018

Angel-Fernandez, Julian M. & Yiannoutsou, Nikoleta & Kynigos, Chronis & Girvan, Carina & Vincze, Markus Constructionism 2018.

Keywords: Educational Robotics, Framework for Educational Robotics, Pedagogical Activities, Educational Activities, Educational Robotics for STEM, and Constructionism

Educational robotics has been considered as a field with a good potential to teach difficult concepts (e.g. friction) in appealing way. As a consequence, the interest in educational robotics has grown in the last decade, which is reflected in increasing number of robotic platforms, kits, and programming interfaces now available. Nevertheless, researches still fail on describe activities that could be used by teachers and other people with no technological fluency, who are scared by the overwhelm amount of information that made them avoid the use of robotics to teach. Moreover, most of the activities

developed until now do not consider pedagogical methodologies to inform the design and implementation of them. As a direct consequence of the misinformation about the correct use of pedagogical methodologies and robotics' multidisciplinary, the number of people who master the use of robotics in education is still scant. This paper presents ongoing work on the development of a framework in the European project Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineer, and Mathematics (ER4STEM). The framework aims to make evident the connection between 21st century skills, robotics and pedagogical methodologies to support the creation of pedagogical activities, which is defined in ER4STEM as an activity that has clear learning outcomes and evidence of learning, use of one or more pedagogic methodologies during the activity, and detail description of the activity. This is achieved through the critical use of tools and examples of activities developed ER4STEM.

Supporting the teaching practice

An important part of ER4STEM approach was to develop innovative educational activities on Educational Robotics aiming to support project partners in the implementation of workshops and provide useful material and support to relevant stakeholders: i.e. teachers, instructors, companies. This aspect of ER4STEM is presented in the following publications which describe the rationale of the Activity plan template which was designed to support practitioners in the design of ER activities. This template after its refinement in the project became the basis for the activity design tool integrated in the repository. The activity plans developed in the life of the project became a basis for the bottom up development of a Generic Curriculum for Educational Robotics. The half-baked approach as demonstrated through game modding (Yiannoutsou & Kynigos 2016) and the integration of ER with the school curriculum (Xenos et al 2017) are two methodological approaches for teaching and learning with ER, introduced and further developed in ER4STEM.

Activity Plan Template: a mediating tool for supporting learning design with robotics: 2016

Nikoleta Yiannoutsou, Sofia Nikitopoulou, Chronis Kynigos, Ivaylo Gueorguiev, Julian Angel Fernandez (UoA, ESI -CEE, TuWien)

Keywords: Activity Plan Template; learning design; educational robotics

Although Robotics have been designed for education for several decades now, only recently they started being broadly used in education, formal and non formal. In this context many different technologies have emerged accompanied by relevant learning material and resources. Our observation is that the vast number of learning activities is driven by multiple "personal pedagogies" and thus it results in the fragmentation of the domain. To address this problem we discuss in the paper the construct of "activity plan template", a generic design tool that will facilitate different stakeholders (teachers, instructors, researchers) to design learning activities for different robotic toolkits. In the paper we discuss the characteristics of the activity plan template and the research process of generating such a template. Since we report work in progress, we present here the first version of the activity plan template, the construction of which is based on a set of best practices identified.

The ER4STEM Repository for Educational Robotics: 2018

Annalise Duca, Angele Giuliano, Sofia Nikitopoulou, Nikoleta Yiannoutsou, Chronis Kynigos (AL, UoA)

Constructionism 2018

Keywords: repository; educational robotics; STEM; robots; sharing ideas; collaboration; Educational Robotics for STEM; Educational Activities; Constructionism; OER

Using robotics in education is an engaging method for student motivation towards STEM subjects and more. Teachers, educators and researchers who are newly experimenting with the use of robots in the classroom are all asking a very similar question. "Where can I find inspiration to introduce constructionism in my teaching?", "What can I do to teach my subject using robotics?" The answer to this is "The ER4STEM Repository" which will be full of educational resources, activity plans and suggestions for educators. "The ER4STEM Repository" has been underpinned by the basic pedagogical theory underlying its' design in constructionism. This happens through an Activity Plan Template. This template is aligned with the Repository and provides a generic design instrument that identifies critical elements of teaching and learning with robotics based on theory and practice and is expected to contribute to the description of effective learning and teaching with robotics.

Learning Programming with Educational Robotics: Towards an Integrated Approach: 2017

XenosMarios, Yiannoutsou Nikoleta, GriziotiMarianthi, Kynigos Chronis, Nikitopoulou Sofia

EduRobotics 2016 Educational Robotics in the Makers Era

Keywords: Constructionism, Programming, Educational robotics

Despite the fact that it has been a few years since robotics entered the school and offered new learning opportunities, educational robotics usually is offered in the context of extra-curricular activity (e.g. a "club") which addresses a limited number of students and participation is based on student personal interest. In this paper we explore the potential of ER when it is integrated in the typical school curriculum. In the study we report here, we integrated ER in the computer science curriculum and all students of a 9th grade class engaged with robotics activities. The rationale underlying the study is that robotics can be used as a medium to motivate students in engaging with programming and support them to negotiate real life problems. Analysis of the data collected, indicate that ER when integrated with the computer science curriculum, can create a rich learning environment where programming is contextualized and students are highly motivated to engage and negotiate important STEM concepts."

Game Kits: Metadesign considerations on game modding for learning: 2016

Yiannoutsou Nikoleta, Kynigos Chronis

Interaction Design and Children (IDC) 2016

Keywords: Game modding; End-Users, Learning; Half-baked microworlds

Today's technologies that blur the distinction between users and designers have empowered end-users to engage with powerful learning activities like game modding. In this paper we discuss the characteristics of modding tools as expressive media that support teachers and students alike, to integrate in games their knowledge and ideas without being restricted by tools bound to the way the game is implemented; i.e. mainly through programming and STEM knowledge. We present work in progress on "Sus-X", a GameKit that generates SimCity like games and provides pedagogically designed modding tools. We explore the expressive power of "Sus-X", through two studies with students that engaged in modification of two different games created with "Sus-X": one game involved urban sustainability and the other involved nutrition.

Discussing digital artefacts under design as a process aiming towards the centre of TPaCK: 2018

Diamantidis Dimitris, Kynigos Chronis

Re(s)ources 2018

Keywords: Professional development, instrumental approach, boundary crossing, turtle geometry.

"The study addresses the illumination of TPaCK knowledge of postgraduate mathematics education students and their progression towards the TPaCKcentre by means of a threaded forum discussion concerning their on-going designs of digital artefacts for pupil meaning-making. We perceived those digital artefacts as living documents under change and studied both students' constructions and their written exchanges to identify how their initial ideas were placed in the TPaCK model and how these could progress. We studied the exchanges between them and their instructors as a boundary crossing process considering the artefacts as boundary objects. Our preliminary results show that the process was effective in helping us with our understanding of both how the students started and how they were challenged to progress towards TPaCK intersections and centre."

Towards a Generic Curriculum for Educational Robotics in STEM: From Scientific Concepts to Technologies and Powerful Ideas : 2018

IvayloGueorguiev, Christina Todorova, Nikoleta Yiannoutsou, Christina Gkreka, Carina Girvan, Pavel Varbanov, George Sharkov, Annalise Duca, Lisa Vittori and Julian Angel Fernandez

Keywords: educational robotics, curricula, robotics, workshop, science, technology, engineering, mathematics, learning, STEM

Constructionism 2018

This paper and its corresponding poster present a "work in progress" concept for the visualization of 19 activity plans, into a generic curriculum map for teaching STEM concepts through constructionist robotics activities. There are six educational paths that represent potential use cases and these have been validated through 148 educational robotics workshops implemented with children between the ages of 7 and 18 in six European countries.

Student engagement with robotics and STEM:

ER4STEM emphasized very much student engagement with robotics emphasizing the importance of multiple entry points and the integration of real world problems. These two aspects which were considered part of the ER4STEM approach were emphasized not only on the design of the activity plans (see D.4.1, D.4.2 and D.4.3) but they were also part of the evaluation process.

Studying real-world societal problems in a STEM context through robotics: 2018

Kynigos Chronis, Grizioti Marianthi, Gkreka Christina (UoA)

Workshop "The near future of Children's Robotics" organized in the Interaction Design and Children Conference (IDC) 2018

Keywords: Educational Robotics, STEM education, Lego Mindstorms, Arduino

In this paper, we will discuss the design and implementation of three educational robotics workshops that focus on the use of robotics for addressing real-world societal problems. Through the workshops, we aimed to investigate how the integration of real-world problems to robotics can provide a multidisciplinary approach for 'child-robot interaction' that allows students to engage with different STE(A)M concepts. In addition, we examined if this integration increased or strengthened students' interest in STEM/robotics education and careers. The workshops were designed and implemented in the context of the European project Educational Robotics for STEM (ER4STEM) with students from different age groups using Lego Mindstorms and Arduino kits."

Offering Multiple Entry-Points into STEM for Young People: 2017

Wilfried Lepuschitz, Gottfried Koppensteiner, and Munir Merdan

International Conference on Robotics and Education RiE 2016

Keywords: STEM, after-school program, camps, workshops, non-profit association, research, education International Conference on Robotics and Education RiE 2016

Enrollment in the STEM fields (science, technology, engineering and math) is not keeping pace with the need. Recent reports indicate a decrease in the number of graduates from STEM fields and a shortage on the job market. Considering these issues, particular attention has been paid developing innovative methods and tools for improved teaching of STEM themes. This work presents an approach involving multiple entry points for young people to engage in the STEM fields. This approach is manifested in the non-profit association Practical Robotics Institute Austria (PRIA) with its activities designed to fill STEM gaps in the Austrian education system and to bring innovative engagement that cannot be found in the classrooms. Thus, STEM literacy is fostered as well as the development of systems thinking, problem solving, and teamwork skills.

Enhancing students' interest in STEM through educational robotics (in Greek): 2016

Grizioti Marianthi, Xenos Marios, Kynigos Chronis (UoA)

Hellenic Conference on Innovating STEM Education (HiSTEM) 2016

Keywords: Educational Robotics, STEM, Constructionism

During the last few years there has been a shift of the educational community towards STEM while several studies have indicated the benefits of STEM in the development of important learning skills. Educational robotics, due to their interdisciplinarity, can be a strong tool for the design of STEM activities. The presented research focuses on educational robotics as a means for motivating students to engage with STEM. As part of this research, there was a series of workshops organized in different greek schools. The aim was to study how and to what level educational robotics activities can strengthen students' interest towards STEM subjects and careers and how they can contribute to meaning generation about STEM concepts.

Overview and interim evaluation of the project ROBIN: Robotics for integration: 2016

Lisa Vittori, Lisamarie Schuster, Nicole Weinert, Gottfried Koppensteiner and Wilfried Lepuschitz

International Conference on Engineering Education (ICEED) 2016

"Statistics in Austria show a significantly higher unemployment rate of people with migration background compared to those without such a background. This situation is further aggravated by the increased application of modern technologies that replace jobs with automated systems. People with migration background in Austria tend to have a lower qualification and corresponding jobs that are in higher danger of being automated. This paper presents the concept of the project ROBIN that employs educational robotics for inspiring young people towards engineering and technology. In this context, a focus is specifically put on supporting young people with a migration background. Also the results of an interim project evaluation are presented and a few lessons learned are discussed.

Technologies

The papers included in this section involve the development of Hedgehog, a Controller for educational robotics, which was developed as part of the work described in WP5.

Hedgehog: A Versatile Controller for Educational Robotics: 2018

Markus Klein, Clemens Koza, Wilfried Lepuschitz and Gottfried Koppensteiner

Constructionism 2018

Keywords: Robotics, Programming, Visual Programming, STEM

We describe Hedgehog, an educational robotics controller designed to foster interest in STEM subjects. Hedgehog allows building robots out of common actuators and sensors, and can be combined with Lego for a beginner-friendly experience. Through building robots, students can learn and apply engineering, electronics, planning and teamwork skills. The controller facilitates learning programming at different age levels through both textual and visual programming support. For advanced students, Hedgehog's open source ecosystem allows delving into subjects such as microcontroller programming or cooperative robots as well. Hedgehog has been used in numerous workshops and also in robotics competitions with great success.

Hedgehog Light – A Versatile, White Box Educational Robotics Controller: 2016

Clemens Koza, Wilfried Lepuschitz, Martin Wolff, Daniel Frank, and Gottfried Koppensteiner

EduRobotics 2016 Educational Robotics in the Makers Era

Keywords: Controller, Raspberry Pi, white box, open source, programming

Robotics curricula that include programming generally require a robotics controller as core platform. The controller and its capabilities shape the offered curriculum in terms of programming means, and therefore age appropriateness. A closed, black-box controller also limits the uses outside the context of such a curriculum. The Hedgehog Light controller aims to imply as few limitations as possible by using open source methodology, the open and well-documented Raspberry Pi, a multi-platform protocol and programming interface, and that can mostly be built in fabrication laboratories (fab labs).

Architectural Overview and Hedgehog in Use: 2017

Clemens Koza, Martin Wolff, Daniel Frank, Wilfried Lepuschitz, and Gottfried Koppensteiner

Conference on Robotics and Education RiE 2017

Keywords: Raspberry Pi, Controller, Visual programming, Blockly, Python International

Robotics is a versatile tool for teaching STEM topics, as it supports various disciplines, skill sets and target audiences. However, controllers used in Educational Robotics are often limited in their use cases. In this regard, Hedgehog tries to be flexible by design. This paper introduces Hedgehog's architecture, currently implemented and future use cases, and experiences from our first Hedgehog workshops.

Storytelling with Robots

WP4 and specifically D.4.2 identified storytelling as a way of integrating ARTS in Robotics activities, offering multiple entry points and engaging students with Robotics and STEAM. Furthermore, in D.4.2, we outlined the potential of creating a new story genre. Specifically, we identified that robot-related stories offered a meaningful context for robot construction and programming but they also supported generation of stories which integrated and took into consideration the functionalities of the robots. Although the papers included here, can also fall under the category of papers that discuss "student engagement with robotics and STEM", we considered that storytelling can be a category on its own due to its potential to evolve further.

Storytelling as educational strategy for STE(A)M activities that aim to motivate students: A case study: 2018

Panagiotou Evrikia, Diamantidis Dimitris (UoA)

"11th International Conference ICT in Education", 19-21 October 2018, Thessaloniki, Greece"

Keywords: Story telling, multidisciplinary, creativity, educational robotics

In recent years there has been a shift in the educational community towards STEAM fields and their benefits for students in developing important skills for the 21st century. Many studies have highlighted the contribution of educational robotics in the design of STEAM activities. The study we present in this paper focuses on the use of storytelling as an educational method in a STEAM context in order not only to motivate students to be informed about societal issues, such as the problems of the disabled, but also to encourage them to create their own robots, utilising their knowledge of STEM sciences and their creativity (Arts), while they are discussing about their choices

Introducing Storytelling to Educational Robotic Activities: 2018

Julian M. Angel-Fernandez and Markus Vincze (TUWien)

IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (IEEE EDUCON 2018)

Keywords: Storytelling, Creativity, Robotics, Educational Robotics, Informal Education, Thymio II

Creativity is a skill that has been recognized as one of the 21st century skills. Likewise robotics has been recognized as technology with several features to enthrall children and be used to teach a variety of topics (e.g. Mathematics and programming). This paper presents a study done to verify the impact of introducing a storytelling session in an activity with children from 6 to 18 years old in Austria. A total of 196 participants participated in the workshops, held in the campus of the

university. Quantitative and qualitative data were collected and analyzed. The results showed that the most difficult task for old participants was the collaboration between groups created. Participants also did not mention the use of creativity during the design and implementation of the story. Instead participants referred to the work done with robots and technology. Moreover, participants think that working with robots is interesting and fun.

STEM learning

The majority of the papers fall under this category as they discuss and analyse learning during engagement with Robotics in the context of ER4STEM activities. The papers included here involve learning of 21st century skills (Gueorguiev et al 2018), mathematics (Todorova et al, Kynigos&Zantzou 2017) Electronics (Kynigos et al 2017), Programming and Engineering (Angel Fernandez & Vince 2017, 2018)

Educational Robotics for Communication, Collaboration and Digital Fluency: 2017

IvayloGueorguiev, Christina Todorova, Pavel Varbanov, PetarSharkov, George Sharkov, Carina Girvan, Nikoleta Yiannoutsou, MarianthiGrizioti

International Conference on Robotics and Education RIE 2017

Educational robotics, creativity, collaboration, communication, digital fluency, Arduino, visual programming, robotics in education

This paper is the experience-based summary of the work with the design, implementation and results from an “Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop” under the EU funded Horizon 2020 project „ER4STEM – Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics“. This paper gives an overview of the empirical data obtained from the post-workshop questionnaires, completed by the participants from 13 educational robotics workshops, performed in 7 schools (public and private) in Bulgaria with 312 students (142 girls and 170 boys) in the time period from February 16, 2016 until May 31, 2016. The students were between 7 and 14 years old with the majority of them aged between 9 and 10 years old.

Visualizing mathematics with the MathBot: a constructionist activity to explore mathematical concepts through robotics: 2018

Christina Todorova, Carina Girvan, Nikoleta Yiannoutsou, MarianthiGrizioti, IvayloGueorguiev, Pavel Varbanov and George Sharkov

Constructionism 2018

Keywords: Educational robotics; mathematics; programming; Scratch; primary education;

In this practice paper, we aim to share our experience with the design and implementation of constructionist educational robotics activities tailored to primary school students (4th grade, age 9-11 years) implemented in a series of robotics workshops, which took place within a real school setting in Sofia, Bulgaria. Through this contribution, we will further present an activity plan, which involves student engagement with mathematical concepts (angle measuring and properties of the circle) in order to program the behaviour of a robot. Our paper reports insights on the implementation of the activity plan focusing students' evaluation of their experience during the workshop. These insights are drawn from quantitative data from 131 participants (63 boys and 68 girls), capturing the overall

student attitude. The activity plan behind this set of educational robotics workshops was designed, adapted and piloted in alignment to the guidelines of the Bulgarian national curriculum for mathematics for the 4th grade. However, it could function as a practical example, which could be adapted, enriched and modified to benefit other age groups, nationalities and desired learning outcomes.

RobIn: a half-baked robot for electronics in a STEM context: 2017

(Best work in progress paper award)

Kynigos Chronis, GriziotiMarianthi, Nikitopoulou Sofia (UoA)

Interaction Design and Children (IDC) 2017

Keywords: Educational Robotics; STEM; Boundary Crossing;

"Robotic kits in designs for STEM education are becoming popular during the last few years. However, many of them focus mainly on programming leaving aside the electronics and engineering parts of robotics. In this paper we present RobIn (Robotic Insect), a robotic design that supports the equivalent coexistence of programming, construction and argumentation processes in corresponding educational robotic activities. RobIn challenges students to change it, improve it and expand its prototype robotic skeleton by using every day and affordable materials. We also present a study where RobIn functioned as a boundary object among students from different specializations of a Vocational Technical School."

Constructing the shortest path on a cylindrical surface: 2017

Chronis Kynigos, IoannisZantzos

CERME10

Keywords: Curvature, helix, stereometry, meaning-making, programmable media

Digital media warrant a reappraisal of established conceptual fields and a search for new ones densely providing access to powerful mathematical ideas. This study reports secondary students' meaning making around the notion of intrinsically defined curvature in space by means of a tool integrating programming, dynamic manipulation of variable values and a simulation of 3D space. The study involved 15 ninth grade school students' attempt to design the shortest path between two points on a cylindrical surface are presented in this paper. Camera perusal and zoom allow for a change of viewpoints of the constructed figure. The findings yield meanings around concepts notoriously difficult even in undergraduate mathematics, such as differential stereometry, limits and curvature as systematic trihedron state change.

Determining the Effect of Programming Language in Educational Robotic Activities: 2017

Julian M. Angel-Fernandez and Markus Vincze (TuWien)

6th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN).

Robotics has been suggested as a field of high potential in education and with high expectancy to impact teaching from kindergarten to university. This paper presents a study conducted with the purpose to have a better understanding of the impact of programming languages among participants

of a workshop. An activity, which encompasses ten exercises, was designed and we used three different programming languages (i.e. visual, blocky and text) to program the Thymio robot. A total of six workshops were held using this activity two for each programming language. Qualitative and quantitative data were collected in each workshop. The results suggest that despite the programming language used, participants enjoyed working with robots. Moreover participants with previous experience on programming prefer more advance programming languages.

Engineers Designing and Implementing Activities for School Students: What have we learned? 2018

Julian M. Angel-Fernandez and Markus Vincze

II IEEE World Engineering Education Conference (EDUNINE2018)

Robotics kits are spreading out in the market, becoming more convenient, but more is required to determine their impact on educational activities, such as participants' perceptions and factors that could affect the activity. This paper presents an educational activity, which was designed with two main goals in mind. i) Determine if there is any impact of the programming language used in the activity and ii) create a baseline to change various factors in upcoming workshops. It was started with a series of six workshops held in the campus of the university and taken by 124 participants. Results indicate that in general working with robots is interesting and fun, there is no difference between males and females besides the question/factor of using technology to learn, and working in teams. Nevertheless, they also suggest that participants' previous experience on programming must align with the difficulty level of the workshop.

3 PUBLICATION LIST

The scientific dissemination of the project involves a total of 28 contributions in conferences, two contributions in workshops and two contributions in symposia. The contributions in conferences capture a wide range project presentations in terms of audience (key note speeches) and type of information: conceptual, hands on (workshops) and visual (posters)

- Two keynote speeches delivered by Dr Carina Girvan from the University of Cardiff who was responsible for the coordination of the evaluation of the project.
- Twenty (20) paper presentations
- Two contributions in workshops -demonstrations
- Two posters

In the graph below we offer an overview of these publications presenting the number and type of our publications per year.

Graph 2: ER4STEM publications per year

3.1 KEYNOTES

1. Girvan, C. (2018) Understanding Educational Robotics. Presented at Robotics in Education (RiE), Malta, April 2018
2. Girvan, C. (2018) Designing Educational Robotics Activities for All. To be presented at Inclusive Robotics for a better Society Conference (INBOTS), Pisa, Italy, October, 2018.

3.2 CONFERENCE PAPERS

1. Angel-Fernandez, J. & Vincze, M. (2018) Engineers Designing and Implementing Activities for School Students: What have we learned? II *IEEE World Engineering Education Conference (EDUNINE2018)*. Buenos Aires, Argentina, March 11-14, 2018.
2. Angel-Fernandez, J. & Vincze, M. (2018) Introducing Storytelling to Educational Robotic Activities. *IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (IEEE EDUCON 2018)*. Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain, on April 18-20, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/EDUCON.2018.8363286](https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON.2018.8363286). Best paper in Area 3: Attracting, Engaging and Retaining Human Talent to Engineering
3. Angel-Fernandez, J. & Vincze, M. (2018) Towards a Formal Definition of Educational Robotics. *Sixth Austrian Robotics Workshop (ARW 2018)*. Innsbruck, Austria. May 15 and 16, 2018.
4. Angel-Fernandez, J., Yiannoutsou, N., Kynigos, C., Girvan, C. & Vincze, M. (2018) Towards a Framework for Educational Robotics. *Constructionism 2018*. Vilnius, Lithuania, August 21-25, 2018.
5. Diamantidis, D. & Kynigos, C. (2018) Discussing digital artefacts under design as a process aiming towards the centre of TPaCK. *InRe(s)ources 2018*.
6. Panagiotou, E. & Diamantidis, D. (2018) Storytelling educational strategy for STE(A)M activities that aim to motivate students: A case study (in Greek). *In proceedings of 11th International Conference "ICT in Education"*, 19-21 October 2018, Thessaloniki, Greece
7. Todorova, C., Girvan, C., Yiannoutsou, N., Grizioti, M., Gueorguiev, I., Varbanov, P. & Sharkov, G. (2018) Visualizing mathematics with the MathBot: a constructionist activity to explore mathematical concepts through robotics. *Constructionism 2018*. Vilnius, Lithuania, August 21-25, 2018.

8. Angel-Fernandez, J. & Vincze, M. (2017) Determining the Effect of programming Language in Educational Robotic Activities. *26th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN)*. Lisbon, Portugal, on August 28 to September 1 2017. Doi: [10.1109/ROMAN.2017.8172373](https://doi.org/10.1109/ROMAN.2017.8172373)
9. Gueorguiev, I., Todorova, C., Varbanov, P., Sharkov, P., Sharkov, G., Girvan, C., Yiannoutsou, N. & Grizioti, M. (2017) Educational Robotics for Communication, Collaboration and Digital Fluency. In: Lepuschitz W., Merdan M., Koppensteiner G., Balogh R., Obdržálek D. (eds) *Robotics in Education. RiE 2017. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 630. Springer, Cham
10. Koza, C., Lepuschitz, W., Wolff, M., Frank, D. & Koppensteiner, G. (2017). Hedgehog Light – A Versatile, White Box Educational Robotics Controller. *Educational Robotics in the Makers Era Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 229-232. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-55553-9_19
11. Koza, C., Wolff, M., Frank, D., Lepuschitz, W. & Koppensteiner, G. (2017). Architectural Overview and Hedgehog in Use. In W. Lepuschitz, M. Merdan, G. Koppensteiner, R. Balogh & D. Obdržálek (Eds.) *Robotics in Education. RiE 2017. Robotics in Education Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 630. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 238-249. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-62875-2_21
12. Kynigos, C., & Zantzos, I. (2017). Constructing the shortest path on a cylindrical surface, *CERME 2010 Conference*, 1-5 February 2017, Dublin
13. Kynigos, C., Grizioti, M., & Nikitopoulou, S. (2017, June). RobIn: A Half-baked Robot for Electronics in a STEM Context. In *Proceedings of the 2017 Conference on Interaction Design and Children (IDC)* (pp. 521-526). ACM.
14. Xenos, M., Yiannoutsou, N., Grizioti, M., Kynigos, C. & Nikitopoulou, S. (2017). Learning Programming with Educational Robotics: Towards an Integrated Approach. *Educational Robotics in the Makers Era*, 560, 215. Springer, Cham. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-55553-9
15. Grizioti, M., Xenos, M. & Kynigos, C. (2016) Enhancing students' interest in STEM through educational robotics (in Greek), *Presented In Hellenic Conference on Innovating STEM Education 2016 (HISTEM 2016)*, 16-18/12/2016, University of Athens, Greece
16. Lammer, L., Lepuschitz, W., Kynigos, C., Giuliano, A. & Girvan, C. (2016). ER4STEM Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. In M. Merdan, W. Lepuschitz, G. Koppensteiner & R. Balogh (Eds.) *Robotics in Education. RiE 2016. Robotics in Education Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 457. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 95-101. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-42975-5_9
17. Lepuschitz, W., Koppensteiner, G., Merdan, M. (2016). Offering Multiple Entry-Points into STEM for Young People. In M. Merdan, W. Lepuschitz, G. Koppensteiner & R. Balogh (Eds.) *Robotics in Education. RiE 2016. Robotics in Education Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 457. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 95-101. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-42975-5_4
18. Vittori, L., Schuster, L., Weinert, N., Koppensteiner, G. & Lepuschitz, W. (2016). Overview and interim evaluation of the project ROBIN: Robotics for integration. *2016 IEEE 8th International Conference on Engineering Education (ICEED)*. doi:10.1109/iceed.2016.7856096
19. Yiannoutsou, N., & Kynigos, C. (2016). Game Kits: Metadesign considerations on game modding for learning. In *Proceedings of the The 15th International Conference on Interaction Design and Children* (pp. 583-588). ACM.
20. Yiannoutsou, N., Nikitopoulou, S., Kynigos, C., Gueorguiev, I. & Angel-Fernandez, J. (2016). Activity Plan Template: A Mediating Tool for Supporting Learning Design with Robotics. In M. Merdan, W. Lepuschitz, G. Koppensteiner & R. Balogh (Eds.) *Robotics in Education. RiE 2016*.

3.3 CONFERENCE WORKSHOPS - DEMONSTRATIONS

1. Duca, A., Giuliano, A., Nikitopoulou, S., Yiannoutsou, N. & Kynigos, C. (2018) The ER4STEM Repository for Educational Robotics. *Constructionism 2018*. Vilnius, Lithuania, August 21-25, 2018.
2. Klein, M., Koza, C., Lepuschitz, W. & Koppensteiner, G. (2018) Hedgehog: A Versatile Controller for Educational Robotics. *Constructionism 2018*. Vilnius, Lithuania, August 21-25, 2018.
3. Kynigos, C., Grizioti, M., & Gkreka, C. (2018). Studying real-world societal problems in a STEM context through robotics. *Conference on Interaction Design and Children (IDC) 2018*. arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.03245.

3.4 CONFERENCE ABSTRACTS

1. Girvan, C. & Kynigos, C. (2018) The Value Of Qualitative Data In Large Scale, International Research In Educational Robotics, *Presented at The European Conference on Educational Research (ECER)*, Dublin, August 2018.
2. Girvan, C., (2017) Virtual Robotics: Creating, Collaborating and Constructionist Learning in a Virtual World. *Presented at The European Conference on Educational Research (ECER)*, Copenhagen, August, 2017.

3.5 CONFERENCE POSTERS

1. Daskolia, M. & Kynigos, C. (2018) "The CoCreST project: Co-constructing digital stories about sustainability in the city", *Second International ESCA Conference*, 2018, June 3-5, Geneva Switzerland.
2. Girvan, C., Lepuschitz, W., Gueorguiev, I., Todorova, C., Kynigos, C., Grizioti, M., Giuliano, A., Duca, A., Angel-Fernandez, J., & Vincze, M. (2018) Educational Robotics for STEM: From Workshops to Curricula and Framework, *Presented at Constructionism 2018*, Vilnius, August 2018.
3. Gueorguiev, I., Todorova, C., Yiannoutsou, N., Gkreka, C., Girvan, C., Varbanov, P., Sharkov, G., Duca, A., Vittori, L. & Angel Fernandez, J. (2018) Towards a Generic Curriculum for Educational Robotics in STEM: From Scientific Concepts to Technologies and Powerful Ideas. *Constructionism 2018*. Vilnius, Lithuania, August 21-25, 2018.
4. Angel-Fernandez, J., Gueorguiev, I., Lepuschitz, W., Kynigos, C., Giuliano, A., Girvan, C., Klima, M., & Vincze, M. Educational Robotics for STEM (ER4STEM). *ESERA 2017. Educational Science Education Research Association Conference 2017*, Dublin, Ireland.

3.6 PARTICIPATION IN WORKSHOP:

Kynigos, C. (2017) "Teachers and students designing Digital Games Where Rules and Values Co-Exist". Presented in: *"International Workshop on Computational Thinking and Coding skills"*, Linnaeus University, Vaxjo, 30/10/2017

3.7 PARTICIPATION IN SYMPOSIUM:

Kynigos, C. (2107) “ Designing for and understanding Mathematical Meaning-making with digital expressive media “Mathematics Education Symposium, 14th December 2017, *UCL Institute of Education*, London

3.8 JOURNALS, BOOKS AND BOOK CHAPTERS

At this stage there are no published papers in journals because as we mentioned earlier the project aimed at communicating and developing ER4STEM scientific outputs and ideas in the context of conferences. However, there are plans for publishing a book with the educational activities and the generic curriculum developed in the project (WP2 and WP4). At this stage we will deliver in the project an e-book with all the activity plans that have been developed in the project, the activity blocks and they will be structured according to the curriculum developed in WP2. The editing will focus at this stage mainly on the activity plans who will follow the last version of the activity plan template. At a next stage (towards the end of the year), we plan to contact a publisher and engage into a more thorough editing of the activity plans lead by UoA, where activity plan designers will be invited to participate in the book and revise their activity plans according to the editor’s guidelines. Furthermore, the project has composed a plan for publications in journals based on the work that has been done in the different workpackages. Next we offer an brief overview of the planned journal publications in 2018-2019 based on the outputs of each workpackage:

WP1 – ER4STEM Framework:

- Meta-analysis on Educational Robotics
- ER4STEM Framework

WP2 – Educational Robotics Workshops:

- Implementation of Robotics workshops
- A curriculum for educational Robotics

WP3- Educational Robotics Conference:

- Robotics competitions and conferences

WP4 – Pedagogical design and innovation for Educational Robotics:

- Activity design for educational robotics and activity blocks

WP5 – Technology for Education:

- SLurples
- Hedgehog

WP6 – ER4STEM Evaluation:

- Research methodology for investigating learning with Educational Robotics
- Across countries evaluation
- Learning with educational robotics: Domain learning and 21st century skills

4 ACCESS TO SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

The references to the publications are in the publications section of the project's website <http://er4stem.acin.tuwien.ac.at/publication.html> The list of publications is also available through the Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org> Full text availability of publications is dependent upon licencing agreements of the conferences about whether or not they can be uploaded and in what format.

According to the consortium agreement, partners should also make available to the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications. Following the data management plan (D8.1) only data for which we have a) informed consent to collect for research purposes and b) informed consent to share publicly, will be included in any archive. Therefore, there may be incomplete data sets (versus what is reported in the papers). No data which could be used to identify a person or school will be uploaded (video data, images, etc). All data will be anonymised.

5 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
ER	Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
ERW	Educational Robotics Workshop
Implementation Team	All members of the team that implements the workshop including but not limited to facilitators, teachers, researchers, evaluators and others.
REA	Research Executive Agency
STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

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